
SETTLE FOR A TITLE

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Abstract

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Zusammenfassung

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Acknowledgement

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Chapter 1

Introduction

the subject of study of this thesis is a NEMS device for infrared spectroscopy. The device is a silicone nitride membrane, an image is shown in figure 1.1. The device is a membrane And from the eigenfrequency response of this membrane one can deduce the type of molecule placed on the membrane . Finding the type of molecule on the membrane from the frequency response already works and the device is commercially available and made by invisible light labs under the name EMILIE (see section 1.1. More precisely a sweep over a certain range of infrared light wavelengths is put on the membrane while the eigenfrequency response is measured . The silicon nitrate membrane is in good approximation transparent to infrared light so the only absorption of energy from the light is done by the sample material on the membrane . If the sample material absorbs at a certain frequency of infrared light The membrane's temperature increases and therefore it's eigenfrequency decreases. By this eigenfrequency response a different infrared wavelengths one can obtain An infrared absorption spectrum of the sample material.

In addition to the infrared absorption the eigenfrequency response theoretically also holds information about the position of the Mass Off the probe on the membrane. The membrane has different eigen modes with different mode shapes for example see figure 4.3. Depending on the geometrical placement of the probe different eigenfrequencies of different modes should react differently. From the difference in response of the different modes one can deduce the position of the added mass On the membrane. This Method is known and has been performed for example in [Hanay12]. The aim of the work in this thesis is to Develop a numerical model of the membrane to be able to predict the frequency responses corresponding to certain distributions of mass on the membrane to then be able to deduce the mass distribution of the material on the membrane in a given measurement.

The simulation is carried out by the finite element method using the open source fem package NGSolve .

1.1 The EMILIE™ Device

The subject of this thesis is the EMILIE™ device by Invisible-Light-Labs which is a device for Nanoelectromechanical IR spectroscopy (NEMS-IR). It consists of a prestressed SiN membrane on a chip and can be used in combination with a commercial Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy Device. The aim with this device is to detect and characterize chemical substances sampled on the membrane. As shown in [Timarac-Popovic25], EMILIE™ offers unique advantages e.g. in the chemical characterization and monitoring of nanoplastics. An image of the chip and a commercial FTIR device used in combination with EMILIE™ is shown in figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: **(A)** Emilie device, a SiN membrane on a silicon wafer. **(B)** An FTIR spectrometer (Vertex 70, Bruker Corporation, MA, USA) equipped with the NEMS IR analyzer [Timarac-Popovic25]. TODO: Is it okay that i just took this from jelena? TODO: where can I get the high quality images?

1.2 Notation

In this chapter, the mathematical notation for this thesis is defined.

Non-Scalar variables such as vectors and matrices are printed in bold face.

Differential operators are denoted by the nabla operator ∇ and the corresponding operator, most significantly, the gradient of a field is denoted by ∇ and the divergence by $\nabla \cdot$.

The double contraction or double dot product “:” refers to the inner product of $N \times N$ matrices, so for two matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} there holds $\mathbf{A} : \mathbf{B} = \sum_{i,j=0}^N A_{ij} B_{ij}$.

$\mathbf{1}$ and $\mathbf{0}$ are the identity and zero element of the given vector space in context.

The ∂ symbol before a set indicates the boundary of the set, more specifically if a PDE is solved on a domain Ω then $\partial\Omega$ is the boundary of Ω .

Densities are denoted using ρ , stresses using σ . Since we have a 2D problem, densities have the unit kg/m^2 and stresses have the unit N/m . Whenever a physical density or stress with units kg/m^3 or N/m^2 are used we indicate this with a superscript “3D”. Similarly, we use E to denote the Young’s modulus in 2D with units N/m , so $E = E^{3D} \cdot h$ for a sheet material with thickness h and 3D Young’s modulus E^{3D} .

1.3 NGSolve

The FEM simulations in this thesis have been implemented in the software package NGSolve. Netgen/NGSolve is a high performance multiphysics finite element software. It is widely used to analyze models from solid mechanics, fluid dynamics and electromagnetics. The flexible python interface has made it possible to solve the specific set of coupled PDEs that is of interest for this thesis in a highly parametrized manner. Further Information and the documentation can be found in [NGSolve].

1.4 Usage of LLMs

Full disclosure: An LLM has been used for the grammatical refinement of this thesis. In this process, none of the mathematical, physical or empirical content has been changed. The raw form of the thesis, that has been fed to the LLM can be found under (TODO: provide Link) to verify, that aside from formulations, nothing scientifically significant has been changed. The LLM used is ChatGPT by OpenAI. The prompt used was:

I will provide you with a section of my master's thesis in LaTeX format. Please revise the text to improve its clarity, grammar, and scientific tone, transforming it into proper scientific English suitable for an academic thesis in computational science and technology.

Important instructions:

- Do not alter any mathematical, physical, or empirical content, equations, variable names, or references.
- If you find any mathematical mistakes please make me aware of them but do not conduct any changes.
- Maintain all LaTeX commands and formatting.
- Focus on improving sentence structure, clarity, word choice, and formal tone.
- Avoid redundant expressions and make the language more concise where appropriate.
- Keep the formatting and structure unchanged unless needed for clarity.
- Anything labeled "TODO" will be changed afterwards. Leave it as it is.
- If there are any larger changes that you would suggest like restructuring, let me know but do not change right away.

Once you're ready, I'll begin by pasting the raw LaTeX content.

1.5 Code

The code used for this thesis can be found at <https://github.com/tobias-slowiak/msc>. The simulation itself and lots of utility functions are implemented in the main file `emilie_simulation.py`. The code is designed to run on jupyter notebooks, all data generating code is implemented in the files `notebooks/*.ipynb`. Each file is also translated to a regular python script using `scripts/convert_notebooks.py` resulting in the scripts `scripts/*.py`. In the scripts some features can not be used for example the NGSolve visualizations generated with the function `draw_on_mesh`. To generate the plots in this thesis run `scripts/run_all.py`. The plots for section 4.3.7 are not included in that run, since they take more compute, to generate these, run `scripts/parameter_search.py`. The physically meaningful part of the code and an example of usage is also

printed in section B.

Chapter 2

Theory

In this chapter the underlying theory of this thesis is discussed. Some parts are very brief, since they are well known and can be found in the literature. Some aspects are shown more verbosely and specifically for the usecase of this thesis as the derivation is often quite general in the literature such as in [braess07].

2.1 The finite element method (FEM)

In this section, I give a very brief introduction to the finite element method to define the necessary nomenclature for readers unfamiliar with the specifics of the mathematics of the finite element method. A more in-depth introduction can be found in [braess07]. This section is based on [Faustmann22].

Here, we will see the basics of the FEM using the simplest non-trivial model problem, the one dimensional Poisson equation

$$-u''(x) = f(x) \quad x \in (0, 1) \quad (2.1)$$

where we denote $\Omega = (0, 1)$ as the domain. We introduce homogeneous boundary conditions on the boundary $\partial\Omega = \{0, 1\}$ with

$$u(0) = u(1) = 0. \quad (2.2)$$

Note that equation 2.1 is not a partial differential equation (which is the usual usecase of the FEM) but every part of this chapter can be easily generalized to the higher dimensional poisson equation $\Delta u = f$.

In the FEM, instead of solving the original problem in equation 2.1 we solve the so called "weak form" of the PDE, which we can obtain by multiplying by a test function v which is arbitrary but has to fulfill homogenous Dirichlet boundary conditions (more on that later) and then integrating over the domain, obtaining

$$\int_{\Omega} -u''v dx = \int_{\Omega} f v dx.$$

We do this to reduce the requirements on the differentiability of u as well as to bring the equation in a form more suitable for discretization. We can now use integration by parts to get

$$-u'v|_0^1 + \int_{\Omega} u'v' dx = \int_{\Omega} f v dx$$

and since we required homogenous dirichlet boundary conditions we get the weak form

$$\int_{\Omega} u'v' dx = \int_{\Omega} f v dx. \quad (2.3)$$

Until now we have omitted the requirements on the differentiability of u and v . In our original problem in equation 2.1, u has to be at least twice continuously differentiable, which is too strong of a restriction for many practical applications. In deriving the weak formulation, we have relaxed the problem, such that now u (and v) only have to fulfill that $u, v \in L^2(\Omega)$ and $u', v' \in L^2(\Omega)$ (with L^2 being the space of square integrable functions). In the theory of the FEM this notion is further refined and results in the "sobolev spaces". In the scope of this thesis all functions are in the sobolev space $H^1(\Omega)$ which is the space of functions that are square integrable and that have square integrable "weak derivatives". For the sake of brevity this is not further explained here, but we give an intuition: Functions in H^1 are continuous and are differentiable everywhere but for a set of points where the derivative has jumps that are "well behaved". Additionally, in $H_0^1(\Omega)$ the subscript 0 denotes that the functions also satisfy homogeneous Dirichlet boundary conditions.

For the framework of the FEM it is useful to define the left hand side of this equation as a "bilinear form"

$$a(u, v) = \int_{\Omega} u'v' dx$$

and the right hand side as the "linear form"

$$l(v) = \int_{\Omega} f v dx.$$

It is obvious that l and a are linear in v (and u) since differentiation and integration are linear operations. Later we can utilize this to build a linear system of equations corresponding to our problem.

Since v was introduced as arbitrary, this equation has to hold for every v therefore we can rewrite the weak formulation as the problem: Find u such that

$$a(u, v) = l(v) \quad \forall v \in H_0^1(\Omega). \quad (2.4)$$

We now discretize the space into "finite elements". In our 1D case this means, that we decompose the domain $\Omega = (0, 1)$ into subintervals $T_i = (x_i, x_{i+1}), i = 0, \dots, N$ where x_i is a set of chosen points in the domain. We call the set of subintervals $\mathcal{T} = \{T_i, i = 0, \dots, N\}$ a "mesh" on Ω . The set of points $\mathcal{N} = \{x_i, i = 0, \dots, N + 1\}$ is called the "nodes" of the mesh. The idea is to define "basis functions" that are reasonably simple and that are 1 on a given node and 0 on every other node. The simplest such functions are piecewise linear functions, which we will use here, however one can use piecewise quadratic too and so on. In figure 2.1 an illustration of a piecewise linear basis function $\varphi_i : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ for the node x_i is given.

A "FEM-space" $V_h \subset H^1(\Omega)$ (or in general H^n for a given n) is a function space of all functions that can be written as a linear combination of such basis functions on a given mesh. h usually refers to a representative "diameter" of the elements - in our case the size of the subintervals, which do not necessarily have to be uniform. In NGSolve the order of the basis functions is implemented in the variable "order" of a FEM

Figure 2.1: Visualization of the piecewise linear basis function φ_i .

space object (order 1 means linear, 2 means quadratic etc.). Roughly speaking, a higher order gives a better solution but also takes more computations.

In the FEM we seek a solution to our problem in equation 2.4 on such a FEM space, so we seek a linear combination of basis functions $u_h \in V_{h,0} \subset H_0^1(\Omega)$ such that for any linear combination v_h equation 2.4 is satisfied, but since the equation is linear in u and v it is enough to have the equation be satisfied for every basis function φ_i .

Therefore, our discretized problem is: Find $u_h \in V_{h,0}$ such that

$$a(u, \varphi_i) = l(\varphi_i) \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \quad (2.5)$$

Intuitively speaking each basis function "tests" u_h on it's nodal point of the mesh, hence the name "test-function" for v_h . In Dirichlet problems, the values of u_h on nodes on $\partial\Omega$ are set, and so u_h does not have to be tested there, roughly speaking this is why we demanded v_h to vanish on the boundary.

We now decompose u_h in it's linear combination by defining $\mathbf{u} = (u_1, \dots, u_N)^T \in \mathbb{R}^N$ with $u_h(x) = \sum_{i=1}^N u_i \varphi_i(x)$. Plugging this in to equation 2.6 we get

$$u_j \cdot a(\varphi_j, \varphi_i) = l(\varphi_i) \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \quad (2.6)$$

We now define the "stiffness matrix" $\mathbf{A} = (a(\varphi_i, \varphi_j))_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ and the "load vector" $\mathbf{l} = (l(\varphi_1), \dots, l(\varphi_N))^T \in \mathbb{R}^N$ and "assemble" a linear system of equations (LSE)

$$\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{l}$$

which can be solved to find the discretized finite element approximation u_h to u .

2.2 Eigenvalue problems in the finite element method

In the following we will solve the eigenvalue problem of the 2D wave equation for which some more theory is needed. As will be shown below in section 2.3.2 the 2D wave PDE yields the eigenvalue problem

$$\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{u} = \omega^2 \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{u}$$

that is, we are looking for the eigenvectors $\mathbf{u}_i \in \mathbb{R}^N$ of the matrix $\mathbf{M}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ with eigenvalues $\omega_i^2 \in \mathbb{R}$ where N is the number of elements in the given mesh. For this, we are using the preconditioned inverse iteration (PINVIT), see [Knyazev+Neymeyr03]. The implementation in code has been adapted from [NGSolveEig].

The classical inverse iteration of the eigenvalue problem

$$\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{u} = \lambda \cdot \mathbf{u}$$

is

$$\mathbf{u}^{k+1} = \mathbf{A}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{u}^k$$

where the iterate \mathbf{u}^k converges to the eigenvector \mathbf{u}_i with the smallest eigenvalue λ_1 of \mathbf{A} with rate of convergence λ_1/λ_2 where λ_2 is the second smallest eigenvalue, see [Melenk21]. In spite of its name, PINVIT is not exactly an inverse iteration, but a gradient descent method, which in a special case coincides with the inverse iteration as we will see later.

To improve convergence, instead of solving

$$\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{u} = \omega^2 \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{u}$$

we use a preconditioner $\mathbf{C}^{-1} \approx \mathbf{A}^{-1}$ to solve the equivalent problem

$$\mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{u} = \omega^2 \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{u}.$$

Roughly speaking, the below shown iteration converges slowly, if the condition number of \mathbf{A} is large. If $\mathbf{C}^{-1} \approx \mathbf{A}^{-1}$ then the condition number of the matrix $\mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \approx \mathbf{1}$ in the preconditioned eigenvalue problem is close to optimal. More precisely, if \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{A} are spectrally equivalent, that is if there exist $\gamma_1, \gamma_2 > 0$ such that

$$\gamma_1 \mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{u} \leq \mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{u} \leq \gamma_2 \mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{u} \quad \forall \mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^N$$

then the Rayleigh quotient (see below) converges to the smallest eigenvalue with convergence rate σ^2 , where

$$\sigma = \gamma + (1 - \gamma) \cdot \frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_2}$$

with $\gamma = (\gamma_1 - \gamma_2)/(\gamma_1 + \gamma_2)$, see [Faustmann+Melenk24].

We define the Rayleigh quotient

$$\rho(\mathbf{u}) = \frac{\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{u}}{\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{u}}$$

which is equal to an eigenvalue ω_i^2 if \mathbf{u} is the eigenvector \mathbf{u}_i . Starting from a randomly chosen starting iterate \mathbf{u}^0 we use gradient descent to follow $\nabla \rho(\mathbf{u}^k)$ to find the smallest eigenvalue. For this, we first need to find $\nabla \rho(\mathbf{u}^k)$. We compute

$$\rho(\mathbf{u} + \varepsilon \mathbf{v}) = \frac{(\mathbf{u} + \varepsilon \mathbf{v})^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot (\mathbf{u} + \varepsilon \mathbf{v})}{(\mathbf{u} + \varepsilon \mathbf{v})^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot (\mathbf{u} + \varepsilon \mathbf{v})}$$

for a small $\varepsilon > 0$ and an arbitrary direction \mathbf{v} . We expand this to

$$\rho(\mathbf{u} + \varepsilon \mathbf{v}) = \frac{\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{u} + 2\varepsilon \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{v} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2)}{\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{u}} \frac{1}{1 + 2\varepsilon \cdot \frac{\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{v}}{\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{u}} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2)}$$

we omit quadratic terms in ε and since $1/(1+x) \approx 1-x$ for small x we get

$$\rho(\mathbf{u} + \varepsilon \mathbf{v}) = \frac{\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{u} + 2\varepsilon \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{v}}{\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{u}} \left(1 - 2\varepsilon \frac{\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{v}}{\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{u}} \right)$$

which is

$$\rho(\mathbf{u} + \varepsilon \mathbf{v}) = \left(\rho(\mathbf{u}) + \frac{2\varepsilon \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{v}}{\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{u}} \right) \left(1 - 2\varepsilon \frac{\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{v}}{\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{u}} \right)$$

so by expanding and rearranging we get

$$\rho(\mathbf{u} + \varepsilon \mathbf{v}) = \rho(\mathbf{u}) + \frac{2\varepsilon}{\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{u}} (\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} - \rho(\mathbf{u}) \mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M}) \cdot \mathbf{v}$$

so by comparison of coefficients to

$$\rho(\mathbf{u} + \varepsilon \mathbf{v}) = \rho(\mathbf{u}) + \varepsilon \nabla \rho^T \cdot \mathbf{v}$$

we get

$$\nabla \rho^T = \frac{2}{\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{u}} (\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} - \rho(\mathbf{u}) \mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M}).$$

Since all matrices are square we can write

$$\nabla \rho = \frac{2}{\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{u}} (\mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{u} - \rho(\mathbf{u}) \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{u}).$$

Note, that contained in $\nabla \rho$ is the residual

$$\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{u}) = \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{u} - \rho(\mathbf{u}) \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{u}$$

of our eigenvalue problem. We will see later that the magnitude of $\nabla \rho$ has not influence on our gradient descent algorithm, so since $\nabla \rho \propto \mathbf{R}$ we can follow the residual in the gradient descent.

Remark: In the case of $\mathbf{C}^{-1} = \mathbf{A}^{-1}$ with a standard gradient descent with step size 1 we get the iteration $\mathbf{u}^{k+1} = \mathbf{u}^k - R(\mathbf{u}^k) = \rho(\mathbf{u}^k) \mathbf{A}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{u}^k$ which up to $\rho(\mathbf{u}^k)$ coincides with the inverse iteration of the eigenvalue problem of $\mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{A}$.

Instead of using standard gradient descent with a step size α we use a Reighley-Ritz projection of the eigenvalue problem into the subspace $\text{span}(\mathbf{u}^k, \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{u}^k))$ and solve the small eigenvalue problem

$$\begin{pmatrix} (\mathbf{u}^k)^T \\ \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{u}^k)^T \end{pmatrix} \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{u}^k \\ \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{u}^k) \end{pmatrix} \cdot \mathbf{y} = \omega^2 \begin{pmatrix} (\mathbf{u}^k)^T \\ \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{u}^k)^T \end{pmatrix} \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{u}^k \\ \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{u}^k) \end{pmatrix} \cdot \mathbf{y}.$$

for $\mathbf{y}^T = (y_1, y_2) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ to find the new iterand $\mathbf{u}^{k+1} = y_1 \mathbf{u}^k + y_2 \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{u}^k)$. More generally we are interested in the first num eigenvectors and eigenvalues, so we use num iterands $^j \mathbf{u}^k$ for $j \in \{1, \dots, \text{num}\}$ and solve the eigenvalue problem in the subspace $\text{span}(^1 \mathbf{u}^k, \mathbf{R}(^1 \mathbf{u}^k), \dots, ^{\text{num}} \mathbf{u}^k, \mathbf{R}(^{\text{num}} \mathbf{u}^k))$ to find $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \text{ num}}$ with the new iterands $^j \mathbf{u}^{k+1} = y_{2j} \mathbf{u}^k + y_{2j+1} \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{u}^k)$ for $j \in \{1, \dots, \text{num}\}$. To ensure that the iterands $^j \mathbf{u}^k$ do not converge to the same eigenvector one can orthogonalize $^j \mathbf{u}^k$ in every step, see [Melenk21], but this is not necessary in our case, since solving the eigenvalue problem in the Reighley-Ritz projection conserves $\text{rank}(\text{span}(\{^j \mathbf{u}^k\}))$ as is shown in [Neymayr02, Lemma 3.1].

2.3 PDEs and weak formulation

The simulation is a purely mechanical one, so no thermal and/or electrical effects are considered. We look at two coupled PDEs, first the elasticity PDE, which needs to be solved due to the inhomogenous prestress on the membrane. The inhomogeneity is caused by a prestress in the electrode material that adds to the prestress of the membrane material SiN. Furthermore, when samples are applied to the membrane, the samples themselves might also be prestressed. The second equation is the standard wave equation on the membrane. The two PDEs are coupled by simple forward coupling, so first the stress field on the membrane is calculated in the elasticity equation and then used as a coefficient function in the wave equation.

2.3.1 Elasticity PDE

The PDE for elasticity in solid bodies is very well known, you can find everything in many textbooks for example [Fung01]. Solid mechanics of prestressed structures is less frequently seen in books, however it is still well established. For my own understanding I developed derivation of the PDE that is slightly different

than the standard approach, which is presented in appendix A.1. From this derivation, one finds the PDE

$$\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{g}$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma} : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$ is the stress tensor and $\mathbf{g} : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is an external force density. Since we have no external forces acting on the membrane we can set $\mathbf{g} = \mathbf{0}$ and therefore get the equation of static solid mechanics

$$\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{0}. \quad (2.7)$$

When under load, a body will deform which is measured in the displacement $\mathbf{u} : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$. Intuitively speaking, the displacement will introduce internal stresses in the body counteracting external stresses such that the total sum of stresses is zero. The internal stresses stemming from the displacement of the material are determined by the constitutive relations. We assume an ideal, linear elastic and isotropic material which gives us the constitutive relation

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = 2 \cdot \mu \cdot \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + \lambda \cdot \text{trace}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \cdot \mathbf{1} \quad (2.8)$$

where μ and λ are the Lamé constants and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the strain given with

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\nabla \mathbf{u} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T) \quad (2.9)$$

which are derived in Appendix A.1. In our case, somewhat oximoronically, Lamé's constants are functions in space, so $\mu, \lambda : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, since they are dependent on the Young's modulus E and the Poisson ration ν which are effectively different in the area, where the membrane is perforated. For a closer discussion of this see section A.1.

The Lamé constants are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mu &= \frac{E}{2 \cdot (1 + \nu)} \\ \lambda &= \frac{E \cdot \nu}{1 - \nu^2}. \end{aligned}$$

where $E = E(x, y)$ and $\nu = \nu(x, y)$ with effective parameters on the perforation following [IPerf].

The equation 2.7 is solved on the domain $\Omega = (0, L)^2$ which represents the membrane and with $L = 1 \cdot 10^{-3} m$ in the standard case. The membrane material SiN has a prestress, which we denote as σ_{SiN} , and which gives a prestress function

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{SiN}}(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{\text{SiN}} & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{\text{SiN}} \end{pmatrix} \text{ for } \mathbf{x} \in \Omega$$

The electrodes are made from Au and Cr, and also have a prestress. We will analogously name their pre-

stresses σ_{Au} and σ_{Cr} with

$$\sigma_{Au}(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{Au} & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{Au} \end{pmatrix} \text{ and } \sigma_{Cr}(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{Cr} & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{Cr} \end{pmatrix} \text{ for } \mathbf{x} \in E,$$

where $E = (E_l + E_r) \subset \Omega$ is the domain of the electrodes, which is explicitly given later in equation 3.3 and 3.4.

The stress field on the membrane is then given by $\sigma = \sigma_{SiN} + \sigma_{Au} + \sigma_{Cr} + \sigma_u$, where σ_u is the internal stress in the membrane stemming from the displacement \mathbf{u} .

We can sum the prestresses with $\sigma_p = \sigma_{SiN} + \sigma_{Au} + \sigma_{Cr}$ and plug into equation 2.7 to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot \sigma &= \mathbf{0} \\ \nabla \cdot (\sigma_p + \sigma_u) &= \mathbf{0} \\ -\nabla \cdot \sigma_u &= \nabla \cdot \sigma_p \end{aligned} \tag{2.10}$$

where equation 2.10 can be seen as the basic solid mechanics equation 2.3.1 with the divergence of the prestress as an "external force". In our case, the prestress is piecewise constant. The prestress σ_p can be expressed in terms of a heavyside function. The divergence of a 2D heavyside function is a 2D Delta Distribution. We define $\mathbf{f} = \nabla \cdot \sigma_p$ where \mathbf{f} will be a vector field multiplied by the delta distribution that is nonzero on ∂E and that is perpendicular to ∂E and pointing outward of E . For details see below.

With this we have obtained our first PDE with

$$-\nabla \cdot \sigma_u = \mathbf{f}.$$

To use the finite element method, we have to bring this equation into it's weak form as is shown for example in [braess07]. To do this, we multiply with a test function $\mathbf{v} : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ and integrate to obtain

$$-\int_{\Omega} (\nabla \cdot \sigma_u) \cdot \mathbf{v} \, dA = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{f} \cdot \mathbf{v} \, dA.$$

and by using the product rule

$$\nabla \cdot (\sigma_u \cdot \mathbf{v}) = (\nabla \cdot \sigma_u) \cdot \mathbf{v} + \sigma : \nabla \mathbf{v}$$

we can write

$$\int_{\Omega} (\nabla \cdot \sigma_u) \cdot \mathbf{v} \, dA = \int_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot (\sigma_u \cdot \mathbf{v}) \, dA - \int_{\Omega} \sigma : \nabla \mathbf{v} \, dA$$

and with the divergence theorem we get

$$\int_{\Omega} (\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_u) \cdot \mathbf{v} \, dA = \int_{\partial\Omega} (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_u \cdot \mathbf{v}) \cdot \mathbf{n} \, dS - \int_{\Omega} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_u : \nabla \mathbf{v} \, dA$$

so therefore

$$-\int_{\partial\Omega} (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_u \cdot \mathbf{v}) \cdot \mathbf{n} \, dS + \int_{\Omega} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_u : \nabla \mathbf{v} \, dA = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{f} \cdot \mathbf{v} \, dA.$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_u$ is a function of $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$, so $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_u = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_u(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}))$. Since the membrane is physically fixed on all edges, we can use dirichlet Boundary conditions, therefore the testfunction \mathbf{v} vanishes on $\partial\Omega$ and we get

$$\int_{\Omega} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_u : \nabla \mathbf{v} \, dA = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{f} \cdot \mathbf{v} \, dA \quad (2.11)$$

which is the weak form of the PDE, so the problem is find a function $u \in H_0^1(\Omega)^2$ such that equation 2.11 is satisfied.

The corresponding bilinear form $A : H_0^1(\Omega)^2 \times H_0^1(\Omega)^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is therefore given by

$$A(u, v) := \int_{\Omega} (2 \cdot \mu \cdot \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}) + \lambda \cdot \text{trace}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u})) \cdot \mathbf{1}) : \nabla \mathbf{v} \, dA \quad (2.12)$$

where the strain $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ as a function of the displacement \mathbf{u} is given in equation 2.9.

The most significant lines in code implementing this are

```
def Stress(p, strain):
```

```
    [...]
```

```
    return (2 * mu_fct * strain + lam_fct * Trace(strain) * Id(2))
```

```
a = BilinearForm(InnerProduct(Stress(p, Sym(Grad(u))), Sym(Grad(v))).Compile() * dx)
```

As stated above, $\mathbf{f} = \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_p$ which is $\mathbf{0}$ everywhere but on ∂E . The prestress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_p$ is a heavyside-type step function. It is matrix valued, however the matrix is diagonal with $(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_p)_{11} = (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_p)_{22} =: \sigma_p$. With this, the forcing term is

$$\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_p = \begin{pmatrix} \partial \sigma_p / \partial x \\ \partial \sigma_p / \partial y \end{pmatrix} = \nabla \sigma_p.$$

It is more convenient to calculate $\nabla \sigma_p$, so we will do that. We want to get $\nabla \sigma_p$ for $\sigma_p : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ being a heavyside-type function with it's jump along a curve in \mathbb{R}^2 . The curves interesting for this thesis can be written as the solution set of an equation $\phi(x, y) = 0$. We can write

$$\sigma_p(x, y) = \sigma_{\text{SiN}} + \sigma_{\text{add}} H(\phi(x, y)) + \dots$$

where σ_{add} is the added prestress (from the electrodes or the sample) and with the Heavyside function $H : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ which is 1 for $x > 0$ and 0 otherwise. We only look at the jump along one curve as the result can be

used for the other curves analogously. We can now use the chain rule to find

$$\nabla \sigma_p = \sigma_{\text{add}} \delta(\phi) \nabla \phi.$$

The gradient $\nabla \phi$ is a normal to the curve in the solution set of $\phi = 0$, so the forcing term is in the direction normal to the jump in prestress and it's magnitude is given above. The magnitude of the divergence of ϕ has no physical meaning so additionally we need the constraint $|\nabla \phi| = 1$ on the solution set, however this is inconvenient so instead of demanding $|\nabla \phi| = 1$ on the solution set of $\phi(x, y) = 0$ we can more conveniently set

$$\nabla \sigma_p = \sigma_{\text{add}} \delta(\phi) \nabla \phi / |\nabla \phi|,$$

for any ϕ with the desired root, which is what we will do.

This is implemented in code in the function `force_CF`. For the sake of compactness of the text we do not show a plot of the vector field here, however to check correctness the force coefficient function is plotted in `demo.ipynb`.

The forcing term can be implemented in FEM by Interface terms on mesh interfaces, when the mesh is fitted to ∂E which i did. Stress boundary conditions are neumann boundary conditions for the elasticity pde, so the linear form for the force term can be implemented with a prescribed stress of $\nabla \sigma_p$ on the relevant element boundaries, as long as the element boundaries resolve the jumps in prestress. This is implemented in code in

```
f = LinearForm(force_l*v*ds("left_inner") - force_l*v*ds("left_outer") + [...])
```

where "left_inner" is the inner boundary of the left electrode etc. and "coffee_ring_inner" is the inner boundary of the coffee ring of the sample.

Solving $-\nabla \cdot \sigma_{\mathbf{u}}(\varepsilon(\mathbf{u})) = \mathbf{f}$ using FEM gives the displacement field \mathbf{u} with which we can calculate $\sigma = \sigma_{\mathbf{u}} + \sigma_p$ which can be used as the input to the wave equation.

2.3.2 Wave PDE

After obtaining the stress field on the membrane we want to find the eigenfrequencies of the membrane. As shown in section 3.1.1 we can neglect the bending stiffness and only consider the force stemming from the prestress in the membrane. This yields the PDE

$$\nabla \cdot (\sigma \cdot \nabla u) = \rho \cdot \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} \tag{2.13}$$

with $\sigma, \rho, u : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, this is the regular wave equation in 2D.

Here, I also present an intuitive derivation in appendix A.2.

Here, we want to solve the eigenvalue problem, so we set $u(x, y, t) = u_0(x, y) \cdot \cos(\omega t)$. Plugging this into equation 2.13 we obtain

$$-\nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \nabla u_0) = \rho \cdot \omega^2 \cdot u_0.$$

Again, we integrate and multiply with a test function to get

$$-\int_{\Omega} (\nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \nabla u_0)) \cdot v \, dA = \int_{\Omega} \rho \cdot \omega^2 \cdot u_0 \cdot v \, dA$$

Again, we can use the product rule to find

$$\nabla \cdot ((\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \nabla u_0) \cdot v) = (\nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \nabla u_0)) \cdot v + (\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \nabla u_0) \cdot \nabla v$$

and so

$$\int_{\Omega} (\nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \nabla u_0)) \cdot v \, dA = \int_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot ((\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \nabla u_0) \cdot v) \, dA - \int_{\Omega} (\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \nabla u_0) \cdot \nabla v \, dA$$

and again using the divergence theorem and the dirichlet boundary conditions $u_0 = 0$ on $\partial\Omega$ we get

$$\int_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot ((\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \nabla u_0) \cdot v) \, dA = \int_{\partial\Omega} (\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \nabla u_0) \cdot v \, dA = 0$$

so the weak form of our PDE is

$$\int_{\Omega} (\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \nabla u_0) \cdot \nabla v \, dA = \omega^2 \cdot \int_{\Omega} \rho \cdot u_0 \cdot v \, dA. \quad (2.14)$$

The corresponding bilinear form is

$$a(u, v) = \int_{\Omega} (\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \nabla u) \cdot \nabla v \, dA. \quad (2.15)$$

In this case, the right hand side too is a bilinear form

$$m(u, v) = \int_{\Omega} \rho \cdot u \cdot v \, dA.$$

Here, we solve the eigenvalue problem $\mathbf{M}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{u} = \omega^2 \mathbf{u}$ as discussed in section 2.2. The bilinear forms a and m are implemented in code in

```
a += SymbolicBFI(InnerProduct((gfstress * grad(u)), grad(v)))
m += SymbolicBFI(rhofct * u * v)
```

Solving this using FEM yields a modeshape function u and the corresponding angular frequency ω for the first N eigenmodes. These are the results that we are interested in and which we can compare to experimental data.

Chapter 3

Simulation

In this chapter the Simulation is discussed in detail. We will look at the modelling assumptions, the Domain, the Convergence with decreasing element size and the physical parameters and how the results of the simulation fit the experimental data depending on the parameters.

3.1 Assumptions

We make the following assumptions:

- We model the membrane in 2D.
- The bending stiffness of the membrane is negligible. This assumption is backed analytically in section 3.1.1.
- We assume a linear mechanical regime. The displacements on the membrane are small enough such that the elastic behaviour of the material is linear.
- For forward coupling of the two PDEs one has to assume that the deformation of the membrane due to it's vibration is small enough that the change in the prestress of the membrane due to this deformation is negligible.
- We assume that the perforation can be modelled as a continuous part of the membrane with effective density and prestress values.

3.1.1 Influence of the bending stiffness

Here, we analytically show that the bending stiffness of the membrane can be neglected in the modelling. We analytically look at the case of a homogenous square membrane without additional features. In the equation of motion, the forcing from the prestress is given by $\sigma \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}$ whereas the forcing by the bending stiffness is given by $D_p \nabla^2 \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}$, where σ is the prestress and $D_p = E \cdot h^3 / (1 - \nu^2)$ with the Young's modulus E , the membrane height h and the Poisson ratio ν , see [Schmid16]. The equation of motion is then

$$\sigma \nabla^2 u + D_p \nabla^2 \nabla^2 u - \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (3.1)$$

As shown in in [Schmid16], this PDE can be analytically solved by $u : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with

$$u(x, y, t) = u_0 \cdot \sin\left(\frac{n\pi}{L}x\right) \cdot \sin\left(\frac{j\pi}{L}y\right) \cdot \cos(\omega_{ij}t).$$

where $n, j \in \mathbb{N}$, any amplitude $u_0 \in \mathbb{R}$ and the side length of the membrane $L = 10^{-3}m$.

Plugging this into equation 3.1, one can eliminate all the trigonometric factors and obtain

$$-\sigma \cdot \left[\left(\frac{n\pi}{L}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{j\pi}{L}\right)^2 \right] + D_P \cdot \left[\left(\frac{n\pi}{L}\right)^4 + 2 \cdot \left(\frac{n\pi}{L}\right)^2 \cdot \left(\frac{j\pi}{L}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{j\pi}{L}\right)^4 \right] + \rho \cdot h \cdot \omega_{ij}^2 = 0. \quad (3.2)$$

The summand containing D_P will here be called the D_P term and the summand containing σ the σ term. The D_P term is due to the bending stiffness and we will see that it is negligible. First we note that the D_P term is increasing with the mode numbers n and j faster than the σ term since it contains the fourth power of these numbers where the σ term only contains the second. Therefore, the influence of the bending stiffness on the eigenfrequency will be highest on the higher modes. In the results of the simulation, we will only consider modes up to the (3,1) mode, so $n = 3, j = 1$ is the case with the highest influence from the bending stiffness. We can now solve equation 3.2 for ω_{31} specifically compute $\omega_{31} \approx 1.3MHz$. Leaving out the D_P term in equation 3.2, one gets the eigenfrequency under the assumption of zero bending stiffness, which when computed numerically also yields $\omega_{31, nb} \approx 1.3MHz$. More precisely the relative difference of the results with and without bending stiffness is $|\omega_{31} - \omega_{31, nb}|/\omega_{31} \approx 2.7 \cdot 10^{-12}$, the calculations can be found in the file `analytical_case.py` in section B. This result strongly suggests that also in the case with electrodes etc. one can neglect the bending stiffness.

3.2 Domain Geometry

In this section we discuss the implementation of the 2D geometry of the membrane in the simulation. The mesh as it is used in most runs of the simulation is shown in figure 3.1 and can be generated with the function `generate_mesh`. The only cases where a different mesh is used is in the convergence analysis (see section 3.5) and in cases, where a different geometry of the membrane is studied (see section 4.4.2). Additionally, when a sample is put onto the membrane, this is also resolved in the mesh (see section 4.6.2 and the mesh shown in figure 4.4). In the case of the convergence analysis only finer meshes have been used since the mesh in figure 3.1 is the coarsest mesh possible due to the constraint that the electrodes have to be resolved by the mesh. In the case of different membrane geometries, the mesh obviously changes too, however the mesh parameters (most importantly the element size and angles) are very similar.

Figure 3.1: Mesh of the simulation with default parameters. the mesh resolves the electrodes as well as the boundary of the perforated area.

3.2.1 Electrode Geometry

In this section we discuss the geometry of the electrodes and how they were implemented mathematically and in code.

The electrodes are parabola shaped, so we model it with a function

$$f(x) = a \cdot x^2 + b \cdot x + c.$$

The radius of the perforation R_{perf} is kept as open parameters to study the effect of the geometry on the system. With that, a space of $L/2 - R_{\text{perf}}$ is left for the electrodes. Also, the maximum of the parabola f can be adapted. For this we use P_{el} as the percentage of the free space used by the electrodes, so the maximum of the parabola f is $P_{\text{el}} \cdot (L/2 - R_{\text{perf}})$. Solving for the parameters of f we get

$$a = -\frac{4 \cdot P_{\text{el}} \cdot (L/2 - R_{\text{perf}})}{L^2}$$

as well as $b = -a \cdot L$ and $c = w_e/2$ where $w_e = 10 \mu\text{m}$ is the electrode width.

The electrodes therefore lie in the set

$$E_l = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^2 : x < a \cdot y^2 + b \cdot y + c - \frac{w_e}{2} \wedge x < a \cdot y^2 + b \cdot y + c + \frac{w_e}{2}\} \quad (3.3)$$

for the left electrode and

$$E_r = \{(L - x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^2 : x < a \cdot y^2 + b \cdot y + c - \frac{w_e}{2} \wedge x < a \cdot y^2 + b \cdot y + c + \frac{w_e}{2}\} \quad (3.4)$$

for the right electrode, where $L = 1 \text{ mm}$ is the side length of the membrane.

First, we need to implement the geometry of the electrodes in the mesh. For this we need to define points on the faces of the electrodes, which lie in ∂E_l and ∂E_r . In addition to that the possibility is implemented to

have more than one layer of elements across the width of the electrodes for parameter studies (we will see that one layer of elements is enough). Also, for minimal angles between the element edges the points on the faces are placed in a way, that the connecting edge of two neighboring vertices on the two faces is perpendicular to the face. This is done by using the derivative $f'(x) = 2 \cdot a \cdot x + b$ and for a given y coordinate set points on $(f(y) + w_e/2, y + f'(y) \cdot w_e/2)$ for a point on the right boundary and $(f(y) - w_e/2, y - f'(y) \cdot w_e/2)$ for the left. This is implemented in code in the function `points_on_parabola`.

Then, the geometry is needed as a function $g_{el} : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that $g_{el}(\mathbf{x}) = 1$ if $\mathbf{x} \in E_l$ and 0 otherwise. With this one can define the prestress and density. This is implemented in code in the function `geom_el_parabola` and `geom_el_both`.

Furthermore, the geometry of the electrodes is needed in the elasticity problem, because there is an additional prestress on the electrodes which leads to a perpendicular force to the electrode faces in the elasticity PDE. A unit vector perpendicular to the faces of the electrodes $\mathbf{v}_\perp \in \mathbb{R}^2$ can be obtained by using the derivative f' to get a tangential vector $\mathbf{v}_\parallel \in \mathbb{R}^2$ with

$$\mathbf{v}_\parallel = \begin{pmatrix} f'(y) \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \text{ therefore } \mathbf{v}_\perp = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + f'(y)^2}} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -f'(y) \end{pmatrix}$$

which is implemented in code in the function `force_CF`.

3.2.2 Perforation geometry

We model the perforation as a continuous part of the membrane (see section 3.3) the membrane is meshed in the same way as the rest of the membrane. However, we need altered parameters on the perforation and also interface boundary conditions on the boundary of the perforation so the boundary of the perforation is resolved in the mesh. Equidistant nodes on that boundary are placed and connected via labelled edges in the function `generate_mesh`.

3.3 Effective Parameters on the Membrane

We assume that the perforation can be modelled as a continuous part of the membrane with effective density and prestress. The effective density is reduced by the missing mass that is removed by way of the holes. The holes have a radius of $r = 0.297 \mu\text{m}$ and a distance (rim to rim) of r which results in an effective density of $\rho_{\text{eff}} = \rho_{\text{SiN}} \cdot 0.62$.

We assume that the effective prestress on the perforation σ_{eff} is not changed by the perforation so $\sigma_{\text{eff}} = \sigma_{\text{SiN}}$. This assumption comes from the intuition that the stress that was there before making the holes will dis-

tribute over the remaining material and on average stay the same. This is however purely heuristic and will be tested in section 4.3.7.

For convenience, we denote the effective parameters as relative parameters with $\rho_{\text{eff}}^* = \rho_{\text{eff}}/\rho_{\text{SiN}}$ and $\sigma_{\text{eff}}^* = \sigma_{\text{eff}}/\sigma_{\text{SiN}}$.

3.4 Coefficient functions

The equations need multiple coefficient functions as parameters, namely the density, prestress, Young's modulus and Poisson ratio. They are implemented in the functions `generate_rho_fct` and `generate_sig_fct` and `Stress`. Here we present graphical depictions of the density and prestress functions in figure 3.2. The coefficient functions are implemented such that they have the desired values on the electrodes on the nodes on the boundary of the electrodes. Since we have basis functions with degree larger than 0, the basis functions interpolate the coefficient function in a way, that is not a perfect step function. For example, let the density on the membrane be $\rho_m = \rho_{\text{SiN}}^{3D} \cdot h_{\text{SiN}}$ and the density on the electrode be $\rho_e = \rho_m + \rho_{\text{Au}}^{3D} \cdot h_{\text{Au}} + \rho_{\text{Cr}}^{3D} \cdot h_{\text{Cr}}$, then the value of the coefficient function close to and outside of the electrode boundary is not exactly ρ_m . This increases the total mass of the system slightly, however it is reasonable to assume that the effect of this is negligible.

Figure 3.2: (A) Density ρ . (B) Norm of the prestress σ_p with a membrane prestress of $\sigma_{\text{SiN}}^{3D} = 24.7 \text{ MPa}$.

Also, the Young's modulus E and the Poisson ratio ν are piecewise constant coefficient functions and with that also the Lamé Parameters as discussed above. These, however, have a negligible influence on the results.

3.5 Convergence analysis

Since the mesh is by default very fine on the interesting areas (most of all the electrodes) one can expect the results to have a sufficiently small error already at the coarsest possible mesh. Nevertheless, to make sure that the mesh is fine enough, we do a small convergence analysis in `convergence_study.py`. We expect the

fem-eigenvalues $\lambda_{i,h}$ to converge to the real eigenvalues λ_i with convergence rate h^2 where h is the size of the largest element, see [Faustmann+Melenk24]. We see no meaningful convergence, however, the errors with the coarsest possible mesh are already on the order of 10^{-1} , which is in the 6th significant digit of the result and therefore floating point errors most likely obstruct the pure FEM convergence.

3.6 Preconditioners

NGSolve offers a range of preconditioners. These preconditioners are tested for their performance in `preconditioner_study.py`. The eigenvalue problem only reliably converges for the multigrid preconditioner, therefore this was used in all subsequent simulations. With the `bddc` and `h1amg` preconditioners there is convergence in some cases, however they are not reliable and in almost all cases slower than multigrid.

3.7 Fitting of a given Eigenfrequency

The prestress of the given membrane is not known a priori, therefore, the prestress σ_{SiN} has to be determined by the simulation. This is done by repeatedly simulating with different prestresses until a chosen eigenfrequency of the experimental data is fitted sufficiently well. From experience we know that an increase of the prestress of 1 MPa approximately results in an increase of the eigenfrequency of 1 kHz. We start by using an approximated prestress of the membranes. This results in an eigenfrequency of the (i,j) mode of $f_{i,j, \text{fem}}$. We compare this to the frequency $f_{i,j}$ that we aim for with $\Delta f = f_{i,j} - f_{i,j, \text{fem}}$ and then change the prestress by $\sigma'_{\text{SiN}} = \sigma_{\text{SiN}} + \Delta f \cdot L \cdot 1000 \text{ Pa Hz}^{-1} \text{ mm}^{-1}$ (insert the numeric value of L in mm). This is continued until $\Delta f < \varepsilon$ with a chosen convergence criterium of $\varepsilon = 200 \text{ Hz}$.

3.8 Mode detection algorithm

Since we will run a lot of instances of the simulation with varying parameters, it is indispensable to have an automatic detection of the mode corresponding to a given eigenvalue and eigenvector. The algorithm uses a 20 by 20 point grid with the absolute values of the eigenvector on the domain and takes the sum of each row and column of points. Then, peaks in the rows and columns are detected and counted. An eigenvector with i peaks in the column sums array and j peaks in the row sums array corresponds to the (i, j) mode. Our mode detection algorithm is implemented in the function `mode_detection`.

The mode detection has proven to be harder than expected and with the given algorithm not all modes can be detected properly. We have put some effort in the mode detection, however, this version is the one we stuck

with even though it is not perfect. The difficulty in mode detection is illustrated in figure 4.4, where one can see a degenerated (1, 3) mode where the upper and lower peak have split.

3.9 Prestress estimation

One aim of this project is to give a better estimate of the prestress of the SiN membrane. Until now the prestress has been roughly estimated by assuming a homogenous membrane, neglecting the electrodes and the perforation. In the scope of this thesis a script to estimate the prestress using the NGSolve simulation has been developed. The script can be found at https://github.com/tobias-slowiak/calculate_prestress. There, the prestress is first estimated and then calculated by using the simulation. The estimation is done by using a quadratic fit to a set of data points previously made using the simulation. In figure 3.3 these data points and the quadratic fit is shown. Also, the rough estimate assuming a homogenous membrane is shown, which can be calculated from

$$\sigma \approx f_{(1,1)}^2 \cdot \rho_{\text{SiN}} \cdot 2 \cdot L^2$$

where $f_{(1,1)}^2$ is the measured frequency of the (1,1) mode, and L is the side length of the membrane, see [Schmid16].

Figure 3.3: Prestress estimation using a quadratic fit to a set of data points coming from the simulation. For comparison, the corresponding curve of estimated prestresses assuming a homogenous membrane is shown.

3.10 Implementation of sampled masses

At this point, two methods of sample deposition have been carried out for the EMILIE device [Timarac-Popovic25]. One is Aerosolization method for particle deposition where an gas is pumped through the perforation, resulting in aerosol depositon on the membrane (**TODO: also cite Real-time single airborne nanoparticle detection with nanomechanical resonant filter-fiber here?**). The other is Nanoliter droplet

dispensing where a pre-mixed dispersion droplet containing nanoplastic particles was put onto the membrane. After evaporation of the solvent, a residue of nanoplastic particles stays on the membrane. Due to the coffee ring effect [Mampallil18] most of the mass of the residue is deposited along the rim of the droplet (see figure 3.4).

Figure 3.4: Formation of a coffee ring from a Polystyrene solution droplet sampled on an EMILIE membrane.

In the scope of this thesis, only the Nanoliter droplet dispensing method has been considered, however a mass distribution resembling any other application technique could be easily implemented. In the following we will show how the sampled mass has been modeled in the simulation.

The measurement results suggest, that the sampled material itself has a prestress which can also be modeled in our simulation. The Parameters of the simulation p contain a python dictionary $p["added_masses"]$ which itself contains tuples with variables listed in 3.1. Aside from the self explanatory parameters there is `coffee_ring_perctg` which is the percentage of the sampled mass which is located on the ring, the rest is located within the ring. `coffee_prestress` is the prestress within the coffee ring, `non_coffee_prestress` is the prestress of the material within the ring, SEM images suggest that the prestress within the ring is low to zero, since the nanoparticles are relatively far apart, see [Timarac-Popovic25].

If $p["added_masses"]$ is not empty the function `MakeGeometry(p)` adds nodes to the mesh on the boundaries of the coffee ring. The function `generate_sig_fct(p)` sets the prestress on and within the coffee ring and the function `generate_rho_fct(p)` sets the increased mass density on and within the coffee ring according to the parameters. Finally, the function `force_CF(p, x, y)` incorporates the forcing term resulting from the jump in prestress on the boundary of the coffee ring as discussed in section 2.3.1.

3.11 Parameters

In this section we show the adaptable parameters of the simulation and their default values. In the simulation, the letter `p` is reserved for the set of these parameters and is implemented as python dictionary. The adaptable parameters are listed in table 3.1. `p` contains more variables, however these are calculated from the given parameters in 3.1. The default parameters can be set with the function `set_p_standard`.

Table 3.1: Simulation parameters, their corresponding Python dictionary keys in `p`, descriptions, and default values. The values concerning the added mass are in the dictionary `p["added_masses"][i]` with `i` mostly being 0, since we only have one coffee ring. Mesh- and algorithmic parameters have been left out.

Symbol	Python key	Description	Default value
Materials			
$\sigma_{\text{SiN}}, \sigma_{\text{Cr}}, \sigma_{\text{Au}}$	"sigsin", "sigcr", "sigau"	Prestress	24.7 MPa, 1 GPa, 40 MPa
$\rho_{\text{SiN}}^{3\text{D}}, \rho_{\text{Cr}}^{3\text{D}}, \rho_{\text{Au}}^{3\text{D}}$	"rhosin", "rhoCr", "rhoau"	density (3D) of SiN	3440, 7140, 19 320 kg m ⁻³
$h_{\text{SiN}}, h_{\text{Cr}}, h_{\text{Au}}$	"hsin", "hcr", "hau"	thickness of SiN	50, 10, 90 nm
$E_{\text{SiN}}, \nu_{\text{SiN}}$	"Esin", "nu"	Mechanical	250 GPa · h_{SiN} , 0.23
Geometry			
L	"Lside"	Membrane side length	1 mm
w_e	"el_width"	Electrode width	10 μm
P_{el}	"rel_max_of_electrode"	sec. 3.2.1	0.9
R_{perf}	"Rperf"	Perforation radius	0.3 mm
Perforation		Effective relative values	on perforation
ρ_{eff}^*	"mpercentage_perf"	sec. 3.3	0.62
E_{eff}^*	"Epercentage_perf"		0.362
ν_{eff}^*	"nupcentage_perf"		1.0
$\sigma_{\text{eff}}^* - 1$	"corr_perf_sig"		0.0
Added masses			
$x_{\text{samp}}, y_{\text{samp}}$	"x_coord", "y_coord"	coffee ring center	0.5 mm
m_{samp}	"mass"	mass of the sample	0 kg
R_{samp}	"radius"	radius of the sample	0.25 mm
	"coffee_ring_perctg"	sec. 3.10	0.8
σ_{samp}	"coffee_prestress"	sec. 3.10	0 MPa
w_{samp}	"coffee_ring_width"	width of ring	5 μm

TODO: change corr perf sig to sigpercentage perf here and in the simulation.

TODO: should i reference where i have constants from e.g. density of gold etc.?

3.12 Simulation with timeout

We found that the PINVIT algorithm does not converge for every set of parameters. Therefore, a wrapper with timeout has been implemented. This implementation can be found in the wrapper function `solve_wrapper` as well as the main function `solve_with_timeout`. A separate process running `solve_wrapper` is instantiated using the python multiprocessing library. For larger simulation runs with a diverse set of parameters this has proven to be very convenient. Due to constraints on the return values in the multiprocessing libraries, the `solve_with_timeout` function can only return the eigenvalues not the modeshapes. Therefore, for small runs where the modeshapes are of interest, the regular solve function is still used.

Chapter 4

Results

In this chapter, we discuss the results of trying to predict the eigenfrequency response of the membrane to a mass distribution using the developed simulation

4.1 Basic Results

In this section we show some basic results including the displacement field resulting from the elasticity PDE and the modeshapes and eigenfrequencies resulting from the wave PDE. How results can be generated can be found in `demo.ipynb`.

In the simulation we first solve the elasticity PDE, which solves for the displacement \mathbf{u} . From this we can calculate the stress field $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_u + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_p$ which is the input for the wave PDE. Both are shown for default parameters in figure 4.1. As one can see when comparing the stress field to the prestress in figure 3.2, the elasticity equation essentially distributes the increased prestress on the electrodes over a larger area resulting in a smaller stress on the electrodes. Also, there are large peaks in the corners of the membrane, however they are still numerically well behaved.

Figure 4.1: (A) Norm of the displacement field \mathbf{u} . (B) Norm of the resulting stress field $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$.

Using the stress field $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ shown in figure 4.1 we can solve the wave PDE. We are most interested in the eigenfrequencies of the membrane since this is what we also aim to measure in the experiment. A comparison of measured resonant frequencies with the eigenfrequencies of the experiment should give a meaningful assessment of the quality of the simulation. For this we use the measured resonant frequencies of a physical membrane, the measurements are further discussed in section 4.5. The prestress of the membrane σ_{SIN} has been determined by fitting the (1, 1) frequency resulting in $\sigma_{\text{SIN}} = 27.8 \text{ MPa}$. The eigenfrequencies of the real membrane as well the simulation are shown in figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2: Eigenfrequencies with the default values of the parameters compared to experimental data using default parameters and a prestress of $\sigma_{\text{SiN}} = 27.8$ MPa.

One can see that the predicted eigenfrequencies of the simulation fit the experimental data correctly within the error bounds. This confirms the validity of the model.

Finally, we show the eigenvectors/modeshapes resulting from the wave PDE. Some selected modeshapes are shown in figure 4.3. One can see that the symmetry of the modeshapes is broken by the electrodes. Figuratively speaking, the peaks of the modeshapes are attracted to mass, which one can see most clearly in the modeshape (3, 1) where the peaks around the electrode are significantly shrunk towards the electrodes. We will see that also the sampled mass "attracts" the peaks as shown in figure 4.1.1.

Figure 4.3: Modeshapes of the membrane with default parameters. Scalar bar for colors has been excluded, since the amplitude of the vibration is dependent on the energy and therefore not set in our context.

4.1.1 Other Modeshapes

The parameters of the simulation obviously influence the modeshapes. In this section we show two interesting cases. These can be found in figure 4.4. Comparing to figure 4.3 one can see that in the case of the (1, 3) mode with changed electrode parameters and with an increased prestress which was implemented to fit the frequencies of membranes from another manufacturer (see section 4.4.1). Here, the top and bottom peak are split in two. This makes our mode detection algorithm fail. A far more specialized algorithm would be needed here. Comparing the (3, 1) mode to the one in figure 4.3 we can see that the middle peak is "attracted" to the sampled mass on the coffee ring. This also almost splits the peak, however in this case the mode detection algorithm still works. With an even larger mass or an increased coffee ring radius the peak would split more and the detection algorithm would fail again.

Figure 4.4: Modeshapes of the membrane. The (1, 3) mode is degenerate due to changed parameters on the electrodes with $\sigma_{\text{SiN}} = 84.9$ MPa, $h_{\text{Au}} = 85$ nm and $h_{\text{Cr}} = 5$ nm. In the (3, 1) modeshape one can see that the peaks are "attracted" to the sampled mass of 40 ng with default parameters and $\sigma_{\text{SiN}} = 27.8$ MPa. Here, the mesh is include to show the position of the sampled mass.

4.2 Comparison to Comsol

TODO: would be cool to compare to the results and also to the computational cost of a comsol simulation

4.3 Parameter Analysis

REMARK: This section is longer than it needs to be. The reason is that until a very late point in the work of this thesis the geometry of the perforation and the electrodes had not been implemented perfectly. A lot of the work for this section had been done at a point where the simulation data did not fit the experimental data too well and we tried to understand which parameters of the simulation could be at fault. Only after that we found that R_{perf} and P_{el} had to be slightly adjusted resulting in the results we have now. Now the results

for default parameters fits almost perfectly and such an extensive parameter analysis would not be necessary. However since the work had already been done and since one can still gain a better intuition about the system via the parameter analysis, we included the work.

In this section we try to understand the impact of different parameters in the simulation on the eigenfrequencies. For each parameter, we give results for the default setting of the parameters and for a reduced and increased version. The results are shown in figure 4.5. The increase and decrease of the given parameter has been set in a way that the effect is well visible in the plot. This should give an idea and intuition of the impact of the parameters. We compare to the unsampled membranes from the production batch also used for the sampled membranes.

The prestress of the membrane is fixed to $\sigma_{\text{SiN}} = 27.8$ MPa which is the value for the experiment determined in section 4.1.

The results in this section can be generated using `parameter_analysis.ipynb` and `parameter_search.ipynb`. The default parameters give the results shown in figure 4.2. We can observe two deviations from the results of a homogenous membrane:

First, the (1,2) and (2,1) modes have different eigenfrequencies and analogously for the third modes. This has to be fully due to the electrodes, since the perforation is symmetric with respect to the of the x- and y-axis. Second, the increase of frequency from the first to the second and third modes is not linear, meaning, the increase in frequency from (1,1) to (2,1) is smaller than that from (2,1) to (3,1). This effect is stronger for the said modes but also there for (1,2) and (1,3). This is due to the perforation and shows, that the perforation relatively effects the first and third modes stronger than the second modes. Note that in the default parameters, the perforation only decreases the effective mass, which increases the eigenfrequency.

4.3.1 Membrane thickness

The results are shown in figure 4.5 (A).

Changing the membrane thickness essentially changes the significance of the membrane mass and prestress relative to the electrode mass and prestress.

Changing the membrane thickness has a larger impact on the (2, 1) and (3, 1) modes than the others. An intuition for this is that it is changing the relative effect of the electrodes, which impact mostly these modes. The (1, 1), (1, 2) and (1, 3) modes seem to be unimpacted. This is somewhat expected since in the case of an ideal membrane, the eigenfrequency is independent of the membrane thickness (see section 3.1).

4.3.2 Radius of the perforation

The results are shown in figure 4.5 (B).

In this case, when changing the radius we simultaneously change the form of the electrodes, since what fixes the electrodes is the percentage of free space taken by the electrodes P_{el} and the free space for the electrodes increases with decreasing perforation radius.

With increasing radius the eigenfrequencies decrease. This is because the total mass also decreases with increasing radius.

What is striking is the relative change in the third frequencies. The (3, 1) frequency is inversely effected by the change in radius. A possible intuition is that the increasing radius of the perforation shifts the electrodes towards the boundary of the membrane and with that onto the side peaks of the (3, 1) mode, increasing its effective mass and therefore slowing it down.

4.3.3 Mass percentage perforation

The results are shown in figure 4.5 (C).

An increased mass percentage on the perforation decreases the eigenfrequencies, since the effective mass of the system is reduced.

The relative effect is slightly larger for the (1, 1), (1, 2) and (1, 3) compared to the (2, 1) and (3, 1) modes. An intuition is that the latter also are effected by the electrodes and the effect of the electrodes is not changed by the perforation mass. What is perhaps surprising is that this effect is very weak, so the frequency change is almost the same for all modes.

The relative change on the first and third modes is stronger than on the second ones. An intuition for this is that the peaks of the second modes overlap less with the perforation.

4.3.4 Prestress on the perforation

The results are shown in figure 4.5 (D).

Our physical intuition said, that the effective prestress on the perforation should be equal to the prestress on the membrane without perforation. Nevertheless, here we inspect the effect of the effective prestress.

An increase in effective prestress leads to an increase in eigenfrequency, which is expected.

It is surprising that the (1, 1) frequency shows almost no effect from a change in relative prestress on the perforation.

TODO: I have no explanation to why this is the case. I double checked if i am not making a mistake in

generating the plot. why is the (1,1) frequency not impacted? i wen up to 0.75 and still the (1,1) was not effected at all...

4.3.5 Thickness of Au

The results are shown in figure 4.5 (E).

Since the bulk of the mass of the electrodes is in the Au part, changing the thickness of Au essentially changes the mass of the electrodes.

The higher the electrode mass the lower the eigenfrequencies. What is interesting is that the (1, 2) and (1, 3) frequencies are also significantly effected by this even though the electrodes have very little overlap with their peaks.

The electrode mass has more influence on the (2, 1) and (3, 1) mode than on the (1, 2) and (1, 3) mode. An intuition on this is that the electrodes intersect with the latter less.

The relative change is larger on the (2, 1) mode than the (3, 1) mode. This is somewhat surprising since the electodes lie more centrally on the side peaks of the (3, 1) mode. A possible intuition is that the middle peak of the (3, 1) does not overlap with the electrodes and therefore it is less impacted.

4.3.6 Thickness of Cr

The results are shown in figure 4.5 (F).

Since the prestress on the electrodes is mostly governed by the prestress of chrome, changing the thickness of the Cr layer in the electrodes essentially changed the prestress in the electrodes.

Increasing the prestress on the electrodes increases the eigenfrequencies.

The effect on the (2, 1) and (3, 1) mode is smaller than on the others. This is surprising since the electrodes act more on these modes. A possible intuition is this: The mass of the electrodes acts more on the (2, 1) and (3, 1) modes since there is more overlap with the peaks. However the prestress of the electrodes acts more on the (1, 2) and (1, 3) modes since the electrodes act like a prestressed string supporting the membrane in y -direction.

Figure 4.5: Eigenfrequencies of the simulation with changes in different parameters. The experimental result is translucently shown as the solid blue graph.

4.3.7 Parameter search

REMARK: Again, we want to point out that the work for this section was conducted in a time when the simulation results did not yet fit the experimental ones well. Since now the simulation fits all eigenfrequencies within the error bounds, there is no point in optimizing parameters. Here we will find parameter sets, which have a smaller loss (deviation from experimental mean values) however, within a proper error analysis, the error is essentially zero in all cases. We nevertheless show the results, since they can give a better understanding of the system.

Here we search for the best set of parameters. Two sets of parameters are not clearly defined a priori, that is the effective parameters of the perforation and the material thicknesses in the electrodes. For the effective parameters of the perforation we do not know if the assumptions made are correct and so it is reasonable to analyse these. The thickness of the electrodes is also not 100 percent clear since they cannot be measured well and it is not clear that they are exactly as suggested by the manufacturer. Therefore, we will optimize the simulation for both sets of parameters here.

We define a loss function $L : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ that measures the error of the simulation with respect two changed parameters P_1 and P_2 with

$$L(P_1, P_2) = \sum_{\{e\}} \sum_{\{m\}} |f_{e,m} - f_{FEM,e,m}(P_1, P_2)|,$$

where $f_{e,m}$ is the measured frequency for mode m of the experiment e and $f_{FEM,e,m}(\sigma_{\text{eff}}, \rho_{\text{eff}})$ is the corresponding frequency from the model using the parameters P_1, P_2 . $\{e\}$ denotes a set of experiments, in this case using membranes from three different manufacturers. This is to ensure, that an improvement of the results is not just "overfitting" one set of eigenfrequencies. $\{m\}$ denotes the set of modes, i.e. $\{(1, 1), (2, 1), (1, 2), (3, 1), (1, 3)\}$. In some cases, not all the modes can be found by the detection algorithm, therefore no loss can be computed for this mode. This squewes the results slightly, however not problematically. In section 4.1.1 we show why in some cases modes can not be found.

The SiN-prestress is set for each experiment, such that $f_{FEM,e,(1,1)} = f_{e,(1,1)}$. The function L is relatively expensive to evaluate, since it has to do one simulation for each experiment in the given experimental data and for each parameter configuration. We nevertheless conduct a gridsearch to understand the behaviour of the simulation better.

Note that the results in this chapter were generated by varying the membrane prestress σ_{SiN} to fit the (1, 1) frequency of the experimental data. We argue why this methodology is sound in section 4.3.7.

The loss with default parameters is $L_{\text{std}} = 19.1(391)$ kHz.

Effective perforation parameters

We vary the effective parameters $\{\sigma_{\text{eff}}^*, \rho_{\text{eff}}^*\}$ on the perforation in a small domain around the default parameters. The results are shown in figure 4.6.

On the given grid we found a minimum at

What is interesting is that the loss landscape forms a valley from high to low σ_{eff}^* and low to high ρ_{eff}^* . An increase in effective density seems to be compensated by a decrease in effective prestress, which seems unintuitive, both work in the way of slower eigenfrequencies. This can be explained by a third factor varying, which is the membrane prestress σ_{SiN} . Since we do not know the values for the effective parameters and since the simulation dictates σ_{SiN} by fitting experimental data, we cannot fix σ_{SiN} . The results here suggest, that decreasing σ_{eff}^* will disproportionately increase σ_{SiN} resulting in higher eigenfrequencies. This does not automatically mean, that this process of parameter search is not physically meaningful. Since we don't know which set $\{\sigma_{\text{eff}}^*, \rho_{\text{eff}}^*\}^*$ comes closest to the actual physical behaviour of the system, we also don't know if the σ_{SiN} we determined by using default parameters is correct and not the one using adapted parameters.

Electrode thicknesses

We vary the parameters h_{Cr} and h_{Au} in a small domain around the default parameters. As one can see there is a valley in the plot in figure 4.6 (A) parallel to the h_{Cr} axis, meaning that the Cr thickness has a rather small impact on the quality of the results. The thickness of the gold membrane has a stronger effect. The minimum loss on the given grid is

$$L(h_{\text{Au}} = 90 \text{ nm}, h_{\text{Cr}} = 8.7 \text{ nm}) = 16.5(391) \text{ kHz}$$

and therefore barely smaller than with default parameters. As the effect of the electrode thicknesses is small and the minimum is very close to the default parameters, we will keep the default parameters.

Figure 4.6: Loss landscapes. (A) Electrode parameters. The simulation did not converge for some parameter sets, these points are left white. (B) Effective parameters on the perforation. The color scale is capped at 50 kHz, some values are larger.

4.4 Membranes with other parameters

We also had membranes with different production parameters available. We measured membranes with higher prestresses and membranes with different sizes from the default size of 1 *mm*. In this section we will compare the results from the simulation with these membranes to validate the simulation over a larger space of parameters. The results can be generated using `other_parameters.ipynb`.

4.4.1 Prestress

Up until now we have used reference values from a batch of membranes made in-house at the technical university of vienna. We also have measurements of other membranes from other manufacturers with vastly different prestress values. Here we compare the results of the simulation to these measurements to verify that the simulation is flexible in its modeling of such membranes. The results are shown in figure 4.7. As one can see, also for these membranes the simulation results fit the experimental ones within the error bounds (except for the (2, 1) mode in figure 4.7 (A) but this is more due to the error being very small.)

4.4.2 Membrane Size

Additionally to membranes with the default size of 1 *mm* side length we also measured membranes with side lengths of 0.5 *mm* and 2 *mm*. In this section we compare the experimental data of these membranes with the simulation results as a verification of the flexibility of the simulation. The results are shown in figure 4.8. Unfortunately we were not able to measure the third modes on these membranes. On the first and second

Figure 4.7: Eigenfrequencies of experiment and simulation for membranes from different manufacturers with different prestresses. (A) Larger prestress from manufacturer Norcada. (B) Slightly larger prestress from manufacturer MS TODO: what is MS really called and how should i cite the names of the manufacturers?.

modes one can see that the simulation results are in good agreement with the data.

TODO: Ich habe leider die Messung der 2 mm chips vermasselt, daher kann ich hier keinen vergleich zeigen. Dazu müsste ich nochmal zum MSA.

Figure 4.8: FEM results compared to experimental data for membranes with a side length of 0.5 mm. The simulation is run with a prestress of $\sigma_{SiN} = 28.0 \text{ MPa}$.

4.5 Measurements

In the scope of this thesis, measurements of the eigenfrequencies of EMILIE membranes with and without sampled materials on it have been conducted. In this section we present the results of these measurements. Note that the following are not the only measurement results made for this thesis. We also have results for other unsampled membranes which have been used in section 4.3 and 4.4 to calibrate and validate the simulation. The eigenfrequency measurements have been carried out on a Polytech MSA-500. For each sampled chemical and mass three membranes from the same production batch have been measured. In the following we present mean values of the respective triplet. The errors are the standard deviation of the measured eigenfrequencies of the three membranes. The sampled membranes have been taken from a batch intended for [Timarac-Popovic25]. There, the eigenfrequencies without IR absorption were not of interest and therefore were also not taken, this is why the following measurements have been carried out. Unfortunately, no unsampled membranes of the corresponding batch have been kept, so we could not measure the unsampled membranes. There are results from shortly after the manufacturing of this batch, however, the eigenfrequencies do not match our measurements (They are too high. We are confident that this is due to the membranes relaxing in the time from the previous measurement to our measurement.). It is however not too bad that we can not study the unsampled membranes since we will see in this section that the eigenfrequency response of the membranes is very small for small masses. We therefore assume with high confidence, that the unsampled membranes would yield results very close to the ones with the smallest mass of 625 pg.

We note here, that there is some room for human error in the measurements. We used a sweep over a relevant range of frequencies for the mechanical excitation of the membrane. Then a spectrum of the response of the membrane has been collected using the Polytec PSV Software. It was not always clear what response peak in the spectrum corresponds to what eigenmode, so there is the possibility that some eigenfrequencies do not correspond to the eigenmodes that we think.

The eigenfrequencies of membranes sampled with Polystyrene (PS) and Polypropylene (PP) are shown in figure 4.9. As one can see, the eigenfrequency response only exceeds the simulation error (which we can qualitatively estimate from section 4.3) at 10 ng and above for PS and not at all for PP. This in itself is maybe the most important result of this thesis: A purely mechanical FEM simulation does not approximate the given system well enough to accurately model sampled masses below 10 ng. Since measurements below this mass are aimed at with the EMILIE device, the approach of this thesis is not applicable practically. In the following chapters we will nevertheless quantitatively study the predictive ability of the simulation. (Note that it still might be possible, that we have 2 opposite effects on the eigenfrequency by the mass of the sample on the one hand and it's prestress on the other. However we will later see, that also without any prestress of the sample the effect of the mass is small.)

Figure 4.9: (A) caption a (B) caption b.

4.6 Simulation results for added masses

Now we want to compare the results of the simulation with added masses to the corresponding experimental data. Since the experimental data shows fundamentally different results for PS and PP we will discuss them separately. For PS, the results suggest, that the PS sample has little to no prestress. For PP the results suggest, that the sampled material has a significant prestress which we will try to model here.

As discussed in section 4.5 we do not have data for unsampled membranes. Therefore we have to determine the prestress using a sampled chip with smallest sample mass. We use the chip sampled with 625 pg PP as a reference which gave us a prestress of 27.1 MPa which was then used for all the other masses including PS.

4.6.1 Polystyrene

The results for this section can be generated from `sample_mass_analysis.ipynb`.

We collected simulation data for added masses from 625 pg to 40 ng since we have experimental data for these values. The coffee rings formed from the droplets naturally have varying radii and shapes, however, looking at them in the microscope it turns out that they all are approximately circle shaped with a pretty constant

radius of approximately $200\ \mu\text{m}$ centered on the perforation. The only significant variance is on the coffee ring widths, which we have implemented in the simulation according to table 4.1 which was generated using microscope data.

Mass [pg]	625	1250	2500	5000	10000	20000	40000
Ring width [μm]	10	10	12	12	15	16	22

Table 4.1: Coffee ring widths of PS taken from microscope images.

For a first impression of the results we plot them similar to figure 4.9 overlaying the experimental data for PS in figure 4.10. For that we set the prestress of the sample to 0. As one can see, the simulation results are in reasonable agreement with the experimental data. For the (3,1) mode, the simulation results are off. This might be due to a measurement error, i.e. that we took the wrong eigenfrequency from the spectrum of the experiment. Of course it might also be due to effects not included in the simulation.

Figure 4.10: Simulation results for the eigenfrequencies of sampled membranes. The experimental data for PS is included translucently.

For better visibility, we look at the relative change of an eigenfrequency with increasing mass. We calculate the average shift in eigenfrequency over all modes except (3, 1). The relative change of the eigenfrequency in experiment vs. simulation is shown in figure 4.11¹. One can see that qualitatively the results match relatively well, however not within the error bounds. More research would be needed to identify the problems leading to this quantitative failure of the simulation. For example we see a different slope from 10 ng to 20 ng compared to 20 ng to 40 ng in the experimental data in figure 4.11. This might be due to different distributions of the material on the membrane that have not been included in the simulation parameters. For example in the microscope images it looks like for 10 and 20 ng there is a smaller circle within the area of the coffee ring where there is more sample mass density whereas in the 40 ng case there seems to be the exact opposite effect (so a smaller circle with reduced sample mass density within the coffee ring).

¹Error bars for the relative frequency change $f_r = (f_s - f_u)/f_u$ with the sampled frequency f_s and unsampled frequency f_u have been calculated using Gaussian error propagation with $\Delta f_r = \Delta f_s/f_u + \Delta f_u \cdot f_s/f_u^2$.

Figure 4.11: Relative shift in eigenfrequency with increasing mass in simulation and experiment.¹

4.6.2 Polypropylene

The results for this section can be generated from `sample_prestress_analysis.ipynb`.

As one can see in figure 4.9 (B) the response of the resonance frequencies to dropmasses of PP strongly differs from PS. In the case of PP, barely any change in eigenfrequency can be found after sampling, independent of the mass of the sample. Here, we model this by introducing a prestress in the sampled material. We will see that with this we can find results that match the experimental data well. Nevertheless this experimental data is bad news for the predictive ability of the simulation since no meaningful shift in the eigenfrequencies means nothing can be deduced from the eigenfrequencies, even if we know the prestress of the material.

First we show the simulation results with default parameters and no prestress as was used for PS. This is shown in figure 4.13 (A). In this case, the eigenfrequencies in the simulation decrease as the mass increases. Looking at the microscope images of the sampled membranes we found that the coffee ring in the 10 ng case had a significantly smaller radius than with the other masses (0.17 mm as opposed to 0.25 mm). Implementing this change in radius in the simulation already accounts for a lot of the stagnation of eigenfrequencies as is shown in figure 4.13 (B). We then increased the prestress in the sample and found an optimal fit to the experimental data with a sample prestress of $\sigma_{PP}^{3D} = 5$ MPa.

The optimal sample prestress has been determined by simulating at different values for σ_{PP}^{3D} and then plotting the average absolute difference of the eigenfrequencies to the experimental resonant frequencies, which is shown in figure 4.12.

One question for this thesis was also if it was possible that the resonant frequencies of a membrane increases when a sample is applied if the prestress is large enough. To study this we looked at a fixed radius of the sample to isolate the effect of the prestress in the sampled material. We found that with the Mass density of PP and the given σ_{SIN} a "reversal" of the effect on the eigenfrequencies happens at approximately $\sigma_{PP}^{3D} = 8$ MPa. To illustrate this, we show the extreme case of a hypothetical prestress of $\sigma_{PP}^{3D} = 50$ MPa in figure 4.13. The radius used here is $R_{\text{samp}} = 0.25$ mm.

Figure 4.12: Average deviation of an eigenfrequency between simulation and experiment. Since the results are already very close to the experimental data, the errors are large, relative to the actual values.

4.7 Conclusions and outlook

The aim of this thesis was to study if it was possible to use a mechanical simulation of the EMILIE device to accurately predict the mass sampled on it from its eigenfrequency response. We find that (at least with the limitations of the simulation in this thesis) this is only possible for relatively large sample masses of 10 ng and above and not for all materials. We did however develop a simulation which can model some aspects of the behaviour of the membrane well. We used this to offer a better estimate for the prestress of the membrane. It should also be possible to calculate the mass distribution on the membrane from a given set of frequency response data. For this a database of many mass distributions and the corresponding frequency response could be calculated using the simulation. The experimental data could then be compared to the simulation data table to determine a likely mass distribution. For sample masses larger than 10 ng the results of this thesis suggest that this might work well. Creating such a table would be easily doable with the simulation framework made for this thesis and also doable with relatively little computational resources.

Figure 4.13: Eigenfrequencies of the simulation with default parameters and varying prestresses of the sample $\sigma_{\text{pp}}^{\text{3D}}$. (A) $\sigma_{\text{pp}}^{\text{3D}} = 0$ MPa with a fixed sample radius of $R_{\text{samp}} = 2.5$ mm. (B) $\sigma_{\text{pp}}^{\text{3D}} = 0$ MPa with a variable sample radius changing to $R_{\text{samp}} = 0.17$ mm at the sample mass 10 ng. (C) Optimal sample prestress $\sigma_{\text{pp}}^{\text{3D}} = 5$ MPa with a variable sample radius. (D) Response of the eigenfrequencies when sampled with a material with density $\rho_{\text{pp}}^{\text{3D}}$ and a hypothetical prestress of $\sigma_{\text{pp}}^{\text{3D}} = 50$ MPa. This is to illustrate how a sampled material with internal prestress can stiffen the membrane. The mode detection algorithm failed the find the (1, 3) mode at 5 and 10 ng.

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Appendix A

Derivations of the PDEs

In this chapter I want to present an intuitive derivation of the PDEs used in this thesis. When studying the elasticity PDE for this thesis, I found that I could understand the standard derivation often found in the literature but that it did not give me a deeper intuition to the equation, especially to the constitutive relation and the shear stresses. I used [Fung01] to learn about the equation and to verify the results of the following derivation, but similar versions can be found in any solid mechanics text book. I then made it a side-project of this thesis to find a derivation that gives me a deeper intuition. None of the following steps are original, they all can easily be translated in the usual derivation. It is just a slightly alternative way of presenting known ideas that gives me a better intuition. Since this was a fun project for me I want to present it here, maybe some of the readers also find it enjoyable. The word "alternative" mostly points to the derivation of the constitutive relation, which I have't seen in the literature in this way. The derivation of the PDEs itself is standard.

A.1 Derivation of the 2D solid mechanics PDE

To derive the constitutive relation of the 2D elasticity equation (i.e. the relation between the stress σ and the strain ε) we look at an infinitesimal square in the plane, shown in figure A.1, which also shows the components of σ and their directions. This can be seen as a definition of all possible stresses acting on a unit square.

We begin with the case of **pure normal stress**, i.e. $\sigma_{xy} = 0$, and subsequently treat pure shear stress, before finally superposing the two cases. First consider the strain in x -direction, ε_{xx} , which arises both from the direct action of the normal stress σ_{xx} and from the Poisson effect due to σ_{yy} . The strain contribution from σ_{xx} follows Hooke's law, so in the case of $\sigma_{xy} = \sigma_{yy} = 0$ we have $\varepsilon_{xx} = \sigma_{xx}/E$. The contribution from σ_{yy} can be expressed using the definition of the Poisson ratio, in the case of $\sigma_{xy} = \sigma_{xx} = 0$ we have $\nu = -\varepsilon_{xx}/\varepsilon_{yy}$, with $\varepsilon_{yy} = \sigma_{yy}/E$. Thus the total strain is the sum of both contributions:

$$\varepsilon_{xx} = \frac{\sigma_{xx}}{E} - \nu \frac{\sigma_{yy}}{E},$$

Figure A.1: Stresses acting on an infinitesimal square at position (x, y) with width dx and height dy . For clarity, not all function arguments of σ are shown.

and by symmetry,

$$\varepsilon_{yy} = \frac{\sigma_{yy}}{E} - \nu \frac{\sigma_{xx}}{E}.$$

Solving these expressions for σ_{xx} and σ_{yy} gives

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{xx} &= \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} (\varepsilon_{xx} + \nu\varepsilon_{yy}), \\ \sigma_{yy} &= \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} (\varepsilon_{yy} + \nu\varepsilon_{xx}).\end{aligned}$$

Next consider the case of **pure shear**, where $\sigma_{xx} = \sigma_{yy} = 0$. This case provides particular physical insight into shear stresses and the material's resistance to it. Conservation of angular momentum requires that the sum of torques is zero. Setting the lower left corner of the infinitesimal square to $x = y = 0$ the only torques left are from the upper and right side with

$$\sum \mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{F} = dx \cdot (dy \cdot \sigma_{xy}) - dy \cdot (dx \cdot \sigma_{yx}) = 0$$

so therefore $\sigma_{xy} = \sigma_{yx}$, which already rules out certain oversimplified depictions of shear, such as those shown in Figure A.2(A).

A useful intuition is that a material's resistance to shear is equivalent to its ability to withstand diagonal loads. This is illustrated by considering the strain along the diagonal e_1 . The infinitesimal square is reinterpreted as an inner square subjected to diagonal forces, as depicted in Figure A.2(C). By distributing the shear forces along the square edges and resolving them into diagonal contributions, one arrives at

$$\begin{aligned}dF_{11,x} &= \frac{1}{2} dx \cdot \sigma_{xy}, \\ dF_{11,y} &= \frac{1}{2} dy \cdot \sigma_{xy}, \\ dF_{11} &= \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{xy} \sqrt{dx^2 + dy^2}.\end{aligned}$$

Figure A.2: (A) The introduction of shear stress is sometimes given this way, with $\sigma_{yx} \neq 0$ and $\sigma_{xy} = 0$. This is not possible, the given setup requires a rigid body rotation additional to shear stresses. (B) Deformation in pure shear case. (C) Illustration of modeling the infinitesimal square as an inner square resiting diagonal load. (D) Infinitesimal forces on the right upper side of the inner square.

Assuming small shear angles, the resulting stress along the e_1 diagonal becomes

$$\sigma_{11} = \frac{dF_{11}}{d_{11}} = \sigma_{xy},$$

with $d_{11} = \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{dx^2 + dy^2}$. By symmetry $\sigma_{22} = -\sigma_{xy}$ since the force can be calculated analogously, however pointing inward not outward, hence the sign change.

Repeating the reasoning of the normal stress case, the strains along the diagonals are

$$\varepsilon_{11} = \frac{\sigma_{11}}{E} - \nu \frac{\sigma_{22}}{E}, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$\varepsilon_{22} = \frac{\sigma_{22}}{E} - \nu \frac{\sigma_{11}}{E}. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Using $\sigma_{11} = -\sigma_{22} = \sigma_{xy}$ yields

$$\sigma_{xy} = \frac{E}{1 + \nu} \varepsilon_{11}, \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$\sigma_{xy} = -\frac{E}{1 + \nu} \varepsilon_{22}, \quad (\text{A.4})$$

which shows $\varepsilon_{11} = -\varepsilon_{22}$.

With this, we found the stress as a function of the strain $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\varepsilon_{xx}, \varepsilon_{yy}, \varepsilon_{11})$. Finally, we want to express the strain $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ as a function of the displacement \mathbf{u} .

We will do this in 2 parts that are partly redundant. First we look at the pure normal strain, which is intuitively easy to grasp. Then we will derive an expression for $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ which shows how shear strain works. Note, that the second part alone would already suffice, we still look at the first example as it explicitly gives an intuition on normal strain.

Pure normal strain: The bottom side of the outer square with side length dx is expanded by $\partial u_x / \partial x \cdot dx$ so

we get

$$\varepsilon_{xx} = \frac{dx + \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x}(x, y) \cdot dx - dx}{dx} = \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x}(x, y)$$

and analogously $\varepsilon_{yy} = \partial u_y / \partial y$.

What is left to find is the dependance of the off-diagonal elements of ε of \mathbf{u} .

Shear strain:

For this, we first perform a polar decomposition of the displacement gradient. Let $d\mathbf{r}$ be the vector connecting 2 points in the material before deformation. Now let u be the displacement. The new vector connecting the same 2 material points in the deformed state is

$$d\mathbf{r}' = (\mathbf{1} + \nabla \mathbf{u}) \cdot d\mathbf{r}. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

From this one can see that, roughly speaking, $\nabla \mathbf{u}$ is very similar to ε (stretching a length l_0 by ε gives $l = (1 + \varepsilon) l_0$). As shown in [Fung01] one can perform a polar decomposition on $\nabla \mathbf{u}$ into a deformation ε and a rigid body rotation ω

$$\nabla \mathbf{u} = \varepsilon + \omega,$$

with

$$\varepsilon = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) \quad (\text{A.6})$$

being the symmetric and

$$\omega = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\nabla \mathbf{u} - \nabla \mathbf{u}^T)$$

the antisymmetric part of $\nabla \mathbf{u}$.

An intuition to why this is the case is the following: Figure A.2 (B) shows an angle θ . For small θ this is equal to the slope of the lower side of the square so $\theta = \partial u_y / \partial x$ and analogously $\tilde{\theta} = \partial u_x / \partial y$. We can now look at 2 cases to find an intuition:

1. Consider the case $\sigma_{xy} = \sigma_{yx} \neq 0$ with no rigid body rotation. Intuitively it should be clear that this causes a deformation of the square as shown in Figure A.2 (B). Mathematically this follows from $\omega_{xy} = 1/2 (\partial u_x / \partial y - \partial u_y / \partial x) = 0$, therefore $\partial u_y / \partial x = \partial u_x / \partial y$ and $\theta = \tilde{\theta}$. With this, the angle in left lower corner of the square is reduced from $\pi/2$. This changes the shape of the square, which the material will resist, so this needs to be considered in the solid mechanics equation. As we have seen above the resistance of the material to this deformation is due to a resistance to normal stress along the diagonal.

2. Consider the case of pure rigid body rotation with $\sigma_{xy} = 0$. With this, the lower side of the square rotate by θ and the left side rotate by the same angle in the same direction with $\theta = -\tilde{\theta}$ (note that $\tilde{\theta}$ is defined to point in the opposite direction of θ , hence the sign). In this case we have $\partial u_y / \partial x = -\partial u_x / \partial y$ so $\nabla \mathbf{u}$ is antisymmetric. The shape of the square is not changed, so there is no resistance of the material to this displacement and therefore we do not need to consider this in the solid mechanics of the body.

Superposing these 2 cases gives the general case with shear deformation and rigid body rotation. For the solid mechanics equation we only need to consider the shear deformation encoded in the symmetric part ε .

What is left to do is to relate ε_{xy} to the strain along the diagonals $\varepsilon_{11} = -\varepsilon_{22}$. In the case of pure shear we have $\varepsilon_{xx} = \varepsilon_{yy}$ so

$$\varepsilon = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \varepsilon_{xy} \\ \varepsilon_{xy} & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

where the eigenvectors of ε are trivially $(1, 1)$ and $(-1, 1)$. By equation (A.5), we see that the diagonal of the infinitesimal rectangle is mapped to an elongated diagonals of the same length iff the diagonals have the same directions as the eigenvectors of ε . Therefore we can relate ε_{xy} to the strain of the diagonal in the case of an actual square with $dx = dy$. In this case, the diagonal extends to

$$\begin{aligned} l_{e_1,d} &= \sqrt{(dx + \tilde{\theta}dy)^2 + (dy + \theta dx)^2} &= \sqrt{(dx \cdot (1 + \theta))^2 + (dy \cdot (1 + \theta))^2} \\ &= (1 + \theta) \cdot l_{e_1,i}, \end{aligned}$$

where we have used $\theta = \tilde{\theta}$ since we consider pure shear. Finally, one can easily see

$$\varepsilon_{xy} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial x} \right) = \frac{1}{2} (\tilde{\theta} + \theta) = \theta.$$

The strain along the diagonal is then

$$\varepsilon_{11} = \frac{l_{e_1,d} - l_{e_1}}{l_{e_1}} = \frac{(1 + \theta) \cdot l_{e_1,i} - l_{e_1}}{l_{e_1}} = \theta,$$

so $\varepsilon_{xy} = \varepsilon_{11}$. We already have found a relation $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\varepsilon_{11})$ in (A.4) so there we can replace ε_{11} by ε_{xy} and with this find our final constitutive relation $\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{u})$ with

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{xx} &= \frac{E}{1 - \nu^2} (\varepsilon_{xx} + \varepsilon_{yy} \cdot \nu) \\ \sigma_{yy} &= \frac{E}{1 - \nu^2} (\varepsilon_{yy} + \varepsilon_{xx} \cdot \nu) \\ \sigma_{xy} &= \frac{E}{1 + \nu} \cdot \varepsilon_{xy}. \end{aligned}$$

For FEM, the formulation of the constitutive relation using Lamé's parameters is more convenient. We define the Lamé Parameters for 2D solid mechanics with

$$\begin{aligned} \mu &= \frac{E}{2 \cdot (1 + \nu)} \\ \lambda &= \frac{E \cdot \nu}{1 - \nu^2}. \end{aligned}$$

With this we can rewrite the constitutive relation of the normal stresses to

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_{xx} &= \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} (\varepsilon_{xx} + \varepsilon_{yy} \cdot \nu) \\
 &= \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} (\varepsilon_{xx} - \varepsilon_{xx} \cdot \nu + \varepsilon_{xx} \cdot \nu + \varepsilon_{yy} \cdot \nu) \\
 &= \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} (\varepsilon_{xx} \cdot (1-\nu) + \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \cdot \nu) \\
 &= \frac{E}{1+\nu} \varepsilon_{xx} + \frac{E \cdot \nu}{1-\nu^2} \cdot \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \\
 &= 2 \cdot \mu \cdot \varepsilon_{xx} + \lambda \cdot \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})
 \end{aligned}$$

and analogously for σ_{yy} . The first Lamé Parameter μ is easily found in the constitutive relation of σ_{xy} and so we can now write the constitutive relation with respect to μ and λ as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = 2 \cdot \mu \cdot \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + \lambda \cdot \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}).$$

Now that we have found the constitutive relation we can go on to deriving the PDE itself. The PDE is basically Newton's second law $F = m \cdot a$. We again look at an infinitesimal square. This infinitesimal piece experiences stresses measured in $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ that cause a resulting force \mathbf{F} which then causes an acceleration \mathbf{a} of the infinitesimal square. We are interested in the static case here, so we set $\mathbf{a} = 0$, therefore $\mathbf{F} = 0$, which already is the sought PDE, the only thing left to find is an expression for the function $\mathbf{F}(\boldsymbol{\sigma})$. As we have seen previously in figure A.1 we have normal and shear stresses acting on each side of the square. Each stress results in a force, and the sum of all forces needs to be zero. The force caused by the stress $\sigma_{xx}(x)$ is $\sigma_{xx}(x) \cdot dy$. Summing all forces and setting to zero we get

$$-\sigma_{xx}(x) \cdot dy + \sigma_{xx}(x + dx) \cdot dy - \sigma_{xy}(y) \cdot dx + \sigma_{xy}(y + dy) \cdot dx = 0$$

in x direction and

$$-\sigma_{yy}(y) \cdot dx + \sigma_{yy}(y + dy) \cdot dx - \sigma_{xy}(x) \cdot dy + \sigma_{xy}(x + dx) \cdot dy = 0$$

in y direction. Dividing both equations by $dx \cdot dy$ and writing in vector form we obtain

$$\begin{pmatrix} (\sigma_{xx}(x + dx) - \sigma_{xx}(x))/dx + (\sigma_{xy}(y + dy) - \sigma_{xy}(y))/dy \\ (\sigma_{yy}(y + dy) - \sigma_{yy}(y))/dy + (\sigma_{xy}(x + dx) - \sigma_{xy}(x))/dx \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

where on the left side only differential quotients are left, so in short

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial \sigma_{xx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{xy}}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial \sigma_{yy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{xy}}{\partial x} \end{pmatrix} = \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

which is the sought for PDE. A new intuition, that arose for me in this step is that for static equilibrium the a change in the normal forces has to be counteracted by a change in the shear forces in both x and y directions. In our model, the changes in in stress are caused by the jumps in the prestress.

A.2 Derivation of the 2D wave equation PDE

This chapter is mostly for completeness, since I have already given an intuitive derivation for the elasticity equation too. The derivation presented here can be found e.g. in [Cleland03].

As stated in section 3.1 we use simple forward coupling to couple from the elasticity to the wave equation. This is achieved by using the resulting stress field σ as a coefficient function in the wave equation. We will assume a resulting $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$ and with that derive the wave equation on the membrane.

Again, the PDE is basically Newton's second law, only that we are now looking at motion outward of the membrane plane. More precisely, we are looking for the displacement $u : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ in z direction. Again we look at an infinitesimal square and Newton's second law on that square. The force F stems from the stress σ in the membrane, and in this case $F = m \cdot a \neq 0$.

We will first look at the normal stresses. Figure A.3 shows an infinitesimal square from the side, looking in y direction. When the square is bent, the sum of the forces caused by σ_{xx} on the left and right side will not vanish, which will result in a force on the square. We only look at displacement of the square in z -direction. As one can see in the vector sketch in figure A.3 the resulting force is not necessarily in z -direction, however, since the stress σ is the result of the solid mechanics PDE, where we demand that the total horizontal force $\mathbf{F} = \nabla \cdot \sigma = \mathbf{0}$, the only remaining component of the force must be in z -direction.

The total force $dF_{x,l}$ stemming from $\sigma_{xx}(x)$ has a slope of $\partial u / \partial x(x)$ so it has a z component of $\partial u / \partial x(x) \cdot \sigma_{xx}(x) \cdot dy$ (recall, that since we are in 2D, σ_{xx} has the unit N/m and so we can omit multiplying with the thickness h) and analogously for $dF_{x,r}$ so the total force in z direction dF_x from σ_{xx} is

$$\begin{aligned}
 dF_x &= \partial u / \partial x(x + dx) \cdot \sigma_{xx}(x + dx) \cdot dy - \partial u / \partial x(x) \cdot \sigma_{xx}(x) \cdot dy \\
 &= \partial u / \partial x(x + dx) \cdot (\sigma_{xx}(x) + \partial \sigma_{xx} / \partial x(x) \cdot dx) \cdot dy - \partial u / \partial x(x) \cdot \sigma_{xx}(x) \cdot dy \\
 &= \sigma_{xx}(x) \cdot \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} \cdot dx \cdot dy + \partial u / \partial x(x + dx) \cdot \partial \sigma_{xx} / \partial x(x) \cdot dx \cdot dy \\
 &= \sigma_{xx}(x) \cdot \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} \cdot dx \cdot dy + \partial u / \partial x(x) \cdot \partial \sigma_{xx} / \partial x \cdot dx \cdot dy + \partial^2 u / \partial x^2(x) \cdot \partial \sigma_{xx} / \partial x(x) \cdot dx^2 \cdot dy \\
 &\approx \sigma_{xx}(x) \cdot \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} \cdot dx \cdot dy + \partial u / \partial x(x) \cdot \partial \sigma_{xx} / \partial x(x) \cdot dx \cdot dy
 \end{aligned}$$

and analogously the same for the stress in y direction is

$$dF_y = \sigma_{yy}(y) \cdot \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \cdot dx \cdot dy + \partial u / \partial y(y) \cdot \partial \sigma_{yy} / \partial y(y) \cdot dx \cdot dy.$$

The shear component of the stress can also cause a force. We set a fixed value y and look at the difference in the shear stress σ_{xy} at position x and $x + dx$. $\sigma_{xy}(x, y)$ has a slope $\partial u / \partial y(x, y)$ with respect to the y axis,

Figure A.3: 1D element under prestress showing tangential stresses causing a backward force in the wave equation.

whereas $\sigma_{xy}(x + dx, y)$ has a slope of $\partial u/\partial y(x + dx, y)$. As with the normal stresses the difference in z direction can be calculated geometrically by comparing the slopes. Analogously to the derivation of dF_x one finds

$$dF_{xy} = \sigma_{xy} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x \partial y} \cdot dx \cdot dy + \partial u / \partial x \cdot \partial \sigma_{xy} / \partial y \cdot dx \cdot dy$$

$$dF_{yx} = \sigma_{xy} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y \partial x} \cdot dx \cdot dy + \partial u / \partial y \cdot \partial \sigma_{xy} / \partial x \cdot dx \cdot dy$$

for the shear forces in the x -direction. We therefore get a total force dF on the square of

$$dF = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} \cdot \sigma_{xx} \cdot dx \cdot dy + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} \cdot \sigma_{yy} \cdot dy \cdot dx + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x \partial y} \cdot \sigma_{xy} \cdot dy \cdot dx + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y \partial x} \cdot \sigma_{xy} \cdot dx \cdot dy$$

$$+ \partial u / \partial x \cdot \partial \sigma_{xx} / \partial x \cdot dx \cdot dy + \partial u / \partial y \cdot \partial \sigma_{yy} / \partial y \cdot dx \cdot dy$$

$$+ \partial u / \partial x \cdot \partial \sigma_{xy} / \partial y \cdot dx \cdot dy + \partial u / \partial y \cdot \partial \sigma_{xy} / \partial x \cdot dx \cdot dy$$

and since $\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{0}$ the last 4 summands cancel out pairwise, so we get

$$dF = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} \cdot \sigma_{xx} \cdot dx \cdot dy + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} \cdot \sigma_{yy} \cdot dy \cdot dx + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x \partial y} \cdot \sigma_{xy} \cdot dy \cdot dx + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y \partial x} \cdot \sigma_{xy} \cdot dx \cdot dy$$

or in short

$$dF = \nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \nabla u) \cdot dx \cdot dy$$

and with $dm = dx \cdot dy \cdot \rho$ (recall that ρ has unit kg/m^2 in 2D) and $a = \partial^2 u / \partial t^2$ we can plug in to $dF = dm \cdot a$ to obtain the sought for equation

$$\nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \nabla u) = \rho \cdot \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Appendix B

Code

Here we present the most important pieces of code from the simulation.

```
123456789 123456789 12345689 123456789 123456789 123456789
```

```
def functione_functione_functione_functione_functione_functione_(functione_, functione_, functione_, functione_):  
    hello_world
```

To-Do List

- Add figures to Chapter 1.
- Complete Chapter 2 conclusion.
- silvan's buch: ist da ein h zu viel bei der kirchhoff love eq?
- silvan's buch: ist die derivation der wave eq. wirklich im timoshenko?
- schauen ob die derivation wirklich so aussieht wie ich will in foundations of nanomech siehe re_foundations_nanomech
- also change nu in the area of the perforation and think about how it would effectively change. I think it should get bigger, but I am not sure. Do a closer discussion in appendix.
- warum schaut die sig und rho function in der added mass so scheisse aus?
- interface BC für added mass
- Die steps in points_on_circle so anpassen, dass die punkte equidistant sind.
- find out why the displacement in the elasticity on the coffee ring is so damn big.
- make all mesh sizes except for the ones on the electrodes hmax, it is too inconvenient setting everything.
- include thought: i did not include nonlinear effects due to the stretch of the membrane. this, however, (i think) can not explain the missing "kink" since this nonlinearity would make the (1,1) mode stiffer relative to the others because it has larger displacements. i want to make the higher modes stiffer, which is (i think) the opposite to what the nonlinearity would do.
- der grund für $\text{sym}(\text{grad}(v))$ ist, dass man die kornsche ungleichung verwenden für koerzivität und das ganze dann in das lax milgram lemma einpflegen kann. die formulierung mit symgrad ist equivalent mit der mit nur grad , weil wir $\sigma:\text{grad}(v)$ betrachten und σ ist symmetrisch, damit kann man zeigen, dass $\sigma:\text{grad}(v)=\sigma:\text{grad}(v)^T$ und damit kann man auch mit $0.5 \text{grad}(v) + 0.5 \text{grad}(v)^T$ multiplizieren und verändert das ergebnis nicht. um das zu zeigen muss man das innere produkt : nur als summenschreibweise anschreiben und die Indizes umbenennen.
- die eindeutige lösbarkeit der elasticity bezogen auf die force lieber mit traction BCs machen, weil die forcing term müsste ein linearer funktional sein (ich glaube das hat faustmann gesagt) und das ist bei der gegebenen delta distribution nicht sicher erfüllt.
- bei der wave equation muss σ von 0 und unendlich beschränkt sein für eindeutige lösbarkeit.

- auf faustmanns homepage das skript zu fem2 anschauen, da steht viel hilfreiches drinnen für eigenwertprobleme, zB dass die mit h^2 konvergieren. Es wird dort auch kurz pinvit erwähnt.
- den beweis dafür dass bei dem eigenwertproblem im rayleigh ritz schritt nicht alle eigenvektoren auf den kleinsten hin konvergieren findet man in dem papaer, das mir faustmann per mail geschickt hat in lemma 3.1. er meinte ich soll das einfach zitieren, mal schauen ob ich das irgendwie verstehen kann falls ja kann ich ja was dazu schreiben aber er meinte er findet es recht unzugänglich.
- ich habe die herleitung des eigenwertproblems eigentlich schon praktisch aufgeschrieben händisch - das noch in die latex datei einbauen. Es sind dabei aber schon noch offene fragen, die ich vielleicht zB mit faustmanns fem2 lösen kann. siehe handschriftlicher zettel
- analyze convergence with different preconditioners
- For the constitutive relation: maybe look for literature for that. accoring to perplexity good literature is <https://www.iperf.org/perforating/knowledge-center/perf-handbook/elastic-properties-perforated-metals/> and <https://utw10193.utweb.utexas.edu/Archive/RuoffsPDFs/285.pdf> and https://research-information.bris.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/168256366/Finite_Element_Modelling_of_Dyneema_Composites_Final_CompA_Reviewed.pdf